

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IBRAHIM****FIRST NAME: FUNSHO****PROGRAM CODE : DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Mac OS High Sierra

EUCLID'S BAPTISMAL COURSEPACK: ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401D coursepack for period one (1) is a well-rounded and rich text, which reviews proper grammar and style, tips for writing papers, logical writing sequences, plagiarism, citation and reference style, differences between the British and American English standards among others. This coursepack aims to indoctrinate “freshers” (new entrants), into EUCLID’s standard of academic writing and style for its various academic programs. The coursepack contains many guidelines and tips including recommendations that endow the student with an arsenal of academic and professional writing tools.

As the student studies the period one (1) coursepack, he or she is likely to feel overwhelmed with the abundant information that it has. At least that was how I felt. Some of this information, the student might be conversant with, some of which he or she ignored or overlooked, and others might appear unexpected, new, or both. Overpowering and complex as the ACA-401D coursepack period one (1) may pose, the good news is that if the student applies the text correctly and rigorously, over time, the student gains a most sought-after skill set that not only stands him or her out among peers but also rank the student among international academic writers.

This response paper contains my reflections on some of the above-mentioned key sections of the period one (1) coursepack. It discusses the areas I have grasped, my findings (either useful, bizarre, or new), where to apply caution, also how I intend to apply the gained knowledge.

2) TIPS FOR WRITING ACADEMIC PAPERS AND LOGICAL SEQUENCE

EUCLID covers the section on writing academic papers and logical sequence in chapters one, two, and three of the period one (1) coursepack. Chapters one and three focuses on the rudiments of essay writing, highlighting three basic steps to include:

- Start the paper early to grasp the topic and vital data in ample time.
- Understand the key issue(s) and establish an approach to take by detecting keywords in the text.
- Draft a plan.

The prerequisite to a good essay entails three principal things: Read, Research, Think and Write (I coined R2TW as an acronym to remember this). Besides these prerequisites, the student needs to examine his response to the essay, and provide the precise answers (EUCLID 2019, 1). EUCLID provides a supplementary reading link from the “Learning Centre Guide,” which I find useful and simplified (ibid.).

Chapter three goes further on writing, suggesting students begin the writing process with a rough draft while considering the draft plan and the paper structure which should have an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. As the writing progresses, EUCLID recommends that students should revise and edit the text, then conclude the process with a last proof-read of the paper plus proper referencing. The points to note are, avoid including last-minute extra information at the conclusion, never lose focus of the essay question throughout the paper writing process, and avoid including “GENERALITIES” (like, In general., It was the greatest discovery of all times, etc.) at the beginning, in the body, or conclusion of the text. Also avoid overusing the phrases “it is...” and “there are...” in sentences.

Chapters one and two addresses logical sequence in writing, and emphasizes on knowing how to use transitions in the paper (EUCLID 2019, 13). Transitions (e.g., on the other hand, alongside, by contrast, more often, etc.) link ideas within sentences and paragraphs (EUCLID 2019, 4). The general idea here is to make things clear and have connected ideas.

This section also looks at how to conduct research for topics alongside tips on reading for essays, the rudiments of note taking, and putting in order one’s ideas. I am reminded to always have the question in mind when taking notes for the essay reading, use evidence to support arguments, and document information sources. When organizing one’s ideas, choose suitable responses, provide examples, and outline talking points in an orderly progression. This brought to mind some lessons learned in the research practices module of my past MBA program. What I found interesting in this section was the tip on structuring an essay paragraph, because it contains new and helpful lessons that I had not come across in past academic pursuit. In short, the structure of an essay paragraph should

have a topic sentence (the key idea or point), supporting sentences, evidence, analysis, and critical conclusion. I have coined an acronym « TSEAC » and also created a word template with this idea. I feel I should use this tip not only to structure an essay paragraph, but structure the entire text, and as a study guide for sourcing information.

3) GRAMMAR

Chapter four (literature review) of the coursepack discusses on grammar, likewise some part of chapter six and eight. The heading literature review could confuse students familiar with research methodology or practice. Literature review in research methodology is the process of searching for published findings related to a research topic; it is an important step before the research writing process. In contrast, literature review in chapter 4 covers essential guidelines on the use of punctuation, grammar, and some aspect of style. The course recommends, using parallel construction, which is the use of similar composition of words to put across important points in a well-ordered fashion, in the essay. It also advocates active voices as a norm in academic writings though, sometimes the use of passive voices (e.g., It should be noted that...) is necessary.

Regarding how to imply possession, the rule maintains, a singular noun should go with an apostrophe before the “s” (e.g., The dog’s food), while the possessive plural nouns should go with an apostrophe after the “s” (e.g., The boys’ hostel). A vital point here is the use of “its” and “it’s.” While “its” states possession, “it’s” is a contraction of “it is.” Same rule applies for “your” revealing possession, and “you’re” as a contraction of “you are.” Another point I learned in this chapter is that, when using the American English style, I must put all punctuation within the quotation marks. Also, in a list of items, I should put a comma between the next to the last item then the conjunction “and” or “or” (EUCLID 2019, 20).

A confusing and somewhat difficult aspect, I found, is the use of “that” and “which.” In the past I had never given it a thought, as I had always relied on grammar checker to make the corrections. The rule of thumb here is “that” comes before restrictive phrases, while “which” comes before nonrestrictive phrases. Restrictive phrases are phrases essential to the sentence’s meaning (i.e., without them, the meaning of the sentence changes), while “nonrestrictive phrases” are non-essential phrases in a sentence (its absence would not affect the meaning of the sentence). A vital information, not mentioned in the coursepack, is the use of commas in “this” and “which.” When you have an adjective clause that begins with “that,” you don’t apply the commas, but, if the adjective clause begins with “which,” you need to put a comma before and after the clause.

Concerning the rule of placing the article “a” in front of a consonant, or “an” preceding a vowel, this rule does not hold entirely. So, the advice here is that if it sounds right to your ear, then it should be ok, better still, consult the dictionary for guidance. I learned as a norm, when using “Good” or “well,” I should use “well” when implying “capably,” or one of the following adjectives: “in good health,” “well-dressed,” “well-groomed,” or “satisfactory,” anything else I should use “good” (EUCLID 2019, 1).

I would add, to conclude this section, avoid hyper-corrections, which occurs when a student tries to sound academic using complex phrases or grammar rules that the student does not understand, including muddled words that affects the clarity of the text.

4) STYLE : SBE VS. SAE / ACADEMIC VS. PERSONAL

A style guide is a basic format or method used, in particular, for academic, business, or technical writing to ensure consistency and clarity. Style is not limited to punctuation, grammar, and lexicon; it involves a lot more as the coursepack ACA-401 D reveals. EUCLID recommends Turabian, a style I am unfamiliar with, for all academic writing. In my previous scholarly writings, I used the APA style. Also, EUCLID has chosen US English format as its preference, though the UK English is acceptable. Henceforth, I am changing my language preference setting in Microsoft word and Scrivener to US English.

I found Chapter eight on Chicago Manual Style (CMS) interesting and educative, I have made a mental note to consult either Merriam Webster's Collegiate Dictionary, Webster's Third New International Dictionary, or both, when in doubt as Euclid recommends (EUCLID 2019, 44). Some rules I grasped concerning style include:

- Unless necessary, do not use an acronym to begin a sentence.
- Only use scholarly abbreviations (e.g., etc,..) within brackets, as comment, in the essay.
- On the whole, avoid using abbreviations unless the reader understands it.
- Always define the meaning of an acronym when using it for the first time in a writeup by putting the acronym's definition before the acronym in a bracket or the inverse. For example, "The Economic Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) arrested the corrupt politician," or "The EFCC (Economic Financial Crimes Commission) arrested the corrupt politician."
- Compound words are double or multiple words combined in a particular order to create a meaning. Pay attention to using compound words in essay writing as it might give a contrary meaning to what you intend. If in doubt, consult a dictionary.
- Hyphenate a prefix when combined with a proper noun, abbreviations in capital letters, and numbers and fractions. For example, post-cold war era, anti-UN slogans, one-third, post-1990s.
- While many prefixes do not have a hyphen (like aftermath, intranet, interstate), there are exceptions that include prefixes having the same linking letters (e.g., Co-op, post-traumatic, non-native), superlatives that precedes only the nouns they modify (e.g., The ill-fated plane crashed), or

prefixes in unversed expressions to simplify its meaning (e.g., Pro-Christ) (EUCLID 2019, 46).

- Avoid using contractions like “isn’t,” “can’t,” “wouldn’t,” “couldn’t.”
- When writing, establish a satisfactory balance between the use of academic and personal style (employ the academic style to write and personal style to give some personal experiences) (EUCLID 2019, 12).

Another aspect of style is the Standard British English (SBE) versus the Standard American English (SAE) which discusses the differences in the two languages in chapter six of the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 27). Comparing SBE to SAE is a complex and extensive subject on its own. The two languages have greater similarities and some differences, particularly in terms of pronunciation and spelling. However, I observed the following key issues:

- SBE and SAE could have same pronunciations but distinct spelling (e.g., diarrhoea/diarrhea, defence/defense, organise/organize), or same spellings but distinct pronunciation (e.g., leisure, ate, schedule).
- SBE and SAE also have some similar words that are either different in meaning or contain extra meanings (e.g., SBE ‘trousers’ = SAE ‘pants’ / SAE ‘pants’ = SBE ‘underwear pants’) (EUCLID 2019, 29).
- SBE uses formal terms, such as ‘shall,’ in contrast SAE uses the more informal ‘will’ or ‘should.’
- Some dissimilarities between SBE and SAE in using large collective nouns (e.g., SBE: Nigeria have lost the match / SAE: Nigeria has lost the match), and in pluralized adjectives (e.g., SBE: John failed his drugs test / SAE: John failed his drug test).

As I mentioned earlier, the list of differences and similarities in the two languages is exhaustive and cannot be covered in this paper. But, I want to believe that the most obvious difference between the SBE and SAE would be in spelling. I feel more comfortable using the SAE, I think it is simpler compared to the SBE.

5) PLAGIARISM

Chapter two of the coursepack discusses plagiarism, citations, bibliography, also when and how to apply them in the essay. Plagiarism, considered an academic dishonesty, occurs when an individual employs a piece of information without citing its author or source. Plagiarism does not just involve copying, quoting or paraphrasing the idea or words of someone, including Internet sources. Getting somebody else to write for you is also plagiarism. Reference the author and the source of the information you use

correctly to avoid plagiarism. When referencing in your writeups, consider including the in-text citations (Direct quotations and Paraphrases) and the bibliography.

Direct quotations, which employ the source of the author verbatim, are in two forms: short and long quotations. For short quotations, insert the text in the quotation marks (“...”) with a parenthesis containing the name of the author and page number. For long quotations (i.e., anything over four lines), the in-text requires no quotation marks and is indented in smaller font size on a separate paragraph. Paraphrasing is the correct depiction of somebody’s idea or work in your exact words, phrase and style alongside citing the author or source. The things to note when paraphrasing is originality, and accurate citation of author or source.

The main idea when referencing in essays is to avoid excessive use of citations, do not cite generally used knowledge or terms, use citations to buttress your points and when the quote defines the subject aptly, spice up your writing with the use of signal phrases in paraphrases or quotations. EUCLID provides the student with a format to follow, when listing a bibliography, in pages 11 and 12 of the coursepack.

6) CONCLUSION

Having gone through the ACA-401D coursepack, I learned lots of additional things. It has so many writing and study tips, and contains so much to keep all at once that I have decided, I have to consult the coursepack every time I pick up my pen to write along with EUCLID’s recommended dictionaries, if I am to make a headway in this academic venture. With determination and constant push for perfection, I will overcome what now looks like a tedious task to accomplish. Welcome to this new challenge!

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. ACA-401/ACA- 401D Coursepack: Period 1. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.